

Generation of picosecond pulses from tapered laser diodes with over 40 W peak power at wavelengths of 780 nm and 830 nm

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Mode-locked diode lasers, with their compact size and low price, are regarded as a promising alternative for the widely used Ti:sapphire lasers and fiber lasers in generating ultrashort optical pulses. Mode-locked quantum well diode lasers emitting at a wavelength of 830 nm have been successfully demonstrated as pulsed sources in terahertz time-domain spectroscopy for non-destructive examination [1], and in two-photon polymerization for 3D micro-structuring [2]. However, a crucial limitation of the application of such diode lasers is their insufficient pulse peak power. A feasible way to improve the pulse energy without additional amplifying stages is to employ a tapered (TP) gain section in the diode laser [3]. In this contribution, we will present monolithic mode-locked laser diodes with TP gain section for the generation of picosecond pulses with high peak power emitting around 780 nm and 830 nm, respectively.

Both epitaxial structures of the lasers comprise an asymmetric AlGaAs large optical cavity waveguide and an active region with a GaAsP single quantum well (780 nm laser) for TM polarized emission or an InGaAsP double quantum well (830 nm laser) for TE polarized emission. Both diode lasers are 6 mm long and consist of a gain-guided TP gain section, an index-guided ridge waveguide (RW) gain section, and an RW saturable absorber, see Fig. 1a. The TP gain section is 3.6 mm long with a full angle of 4° . The RW gain and absorber sections are 2.2 mm and 0.2 mm long, respectively, with a ridge width of $5\ \mu\text{m}$. The TP and RW gain sections are driven in parallel with a gain current I and the saturable absorber is biased with a reverse voltage U . With proper combination of gain current and bias voltage, the lasers operate in passive mode-locking regime. Fig. 1b and c show exemplary pulse performance, i.e. pulse width, peak power, and pulse autocorrelation curves of the two diode lasers.

The 780 nm laser achieves pulse peak power of over 40 W with measured pulse width of ~ 8 ps and a pulse repetition rate of 6.6 GHz, Fig. 1b ($I = \sim 4$ A). The corresponding pulse autocorrelation function and its sech^2 -fit is shown as inset in the figure. The highest peak power from the 830 nm laser is 40 W with a pulse width of ~ 3 ps at a repetition rate of 6.3 GHz, Fig. 1c ($I = \sim 3.5$ A). The pulses generated by both lasers are not transform-limited and can thus potentially be compressed to shorter pulses with higher peak power.

The 780 nm laser is more suitable for two-photon polymerization due to the photosensitivity of the material employed [2]. The 830 nm laser is intended to drive a low-temperature-grown GaAs antenna for THz pulse generation [1].

Fig. 1 schematic diagram of the tapered diode lasers (a) and pulse performance of the 780 nm laser (b) and 830 nm laser (c) with examples of measured autocorrelation function of pulses as insets.

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References

- [1] Surkamp, N., et al. "Mode-locked diode lasers for THz asynchronous optical sampling." Proc. SPIE **10917**, 109171C (2019).
- [2] Zyla, G., et al. "Two-photon polymerization with diode lasers emitting ultrashort pulses with high repetition rate." Opt. Lett. **45**(17), 4827-4830 (2020).
- [3] Krakowski, M., et al. "Stabilized high pulse energy passively mode-locked monolithic and external cavity tapered lasers for space applications." IEEE J. Sel. Top. Quantum Electron. **25**(6), 1-15 (2019).